

Neutrosophic $\pi\gamma^*$ closed sets in Neutrosophic Topological Spaces

Sakthivel K¹ and Gomathi A^{2,*}

¹ Assistant professor, Department of Mathematics, Government Arts College, Udumalpet, Tamil Nadu, India; sakthivelaugust15@gmail.com

* Assistant professor, Department of Science and Humanities, Hindusthan College of Engineering and Technology, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India; gomathimaths12@gmail.com

Abstract: This paper introduces and investigate the notion of Neutrosophic $\pi\gamma^*$ closed sets within the framework of Neutrosophic topological spaces. The study begins defining Neutrosophic $\pi\gamma^*$ closed sets and proceeds to investigate their fundamental properties and characterizations. Special attention is given to examining how these sets interrelate with and extend existing classes of Neutrosophic closed sets. By establishing inclusion relations and comparative hierarchies, the paper highlights the significance of Neutrosophic $\pi\gamma^*$ closed sets in broadening the structural understanding of Neutrosophic topologies. Furthermore, several illustrative examples are provided to demonstrate the distinctive features of these sets and to clarify their role in the generalization process. The paper also derives various theorems that reveal the interplay between Neutrosophic $\pi\gamma^*$ closed sets and other Neutrosophic closed families, thereby enriching the theoretical landscape of Neutrosophic topology. These results contribute to ongoing developments in generalized closed set theory, offering new insights and paths for further research in Neutrosophic mathematics.

Keywords: Neutrosophic topological spaces, Neutrosophic open sets, Neutrosophic closed sets, Neutrosophic $\pi\gamma^*$ closed sets.

1. Introduction

The concept of fuzzy sets, introduced by Zadeh [13] in 1965, allow each element to have a degree of membership. This concept was expanded by K. Atanassov [1] in 1986 with the introduction of Intuitionistic Fuzzy sets, which assign both a degree of membership and a degree of non-membership to each element. Sakthivel K and Manikandan M [10] had studied the concept of $\pi\gamma^*$ closed Sets in Intuitionistic Fuzzy Topological Spaces. Florentin Smarandache [2] introduced Neutrosophic Sets as a further generalization, which adds more flexibility. Later, Salama A A and Alblowi S A [11] extended the idea by developing Neutrosophic Topological Spaces.

In this article we define Neutrosophic $\pi\gamma^*$ closed sets in Neutrosophic topological spaces and investigate their properties.

2. Preliminaries

This section reviews essential definitions, operations, and key results related to Neutrosophic sets.

Definition 2.1 [6] Let X be a non-empty fixed set. A Neutrosophic Set (NS) A is an object having the form $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ where $\mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x)$ and $\nu_A(x)$ represent the degree of membership, degree of indeterminacy and the degree of non-membership respectively of each element $x \in X$ the set A .

Definition 2.2 [6] Let X be a non-empty set and let A be a Neutrosophic Set $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$. Then the complement of A is $A^c = \{ \langle x, \nu_A(x), 1 - \sigma_A(x), \mu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$

Definition 2.3 [6] Let A and B be two Neutrosophic Sets, $\forall x \in X$

$$A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$B = \{ \langle x, \mu_B(x), \sigma_B(x), \nu_B(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$$

Then $A \subseteq B \Leftrightarrow \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \leq \sigma_B(x), \nu_A(x) \geq \nu_B(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$

Definition 2.4 [6] Let X be a non-empty set and let A and B be two Neutrosophic Sets are

$A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$, $B = \{ \langle x, \mu_B(x), \sigma_B(x), \nu_B(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$. Then

1. $A \cap B = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \wedge \sigma_B(x), \nu_A(x) \vee \nu_B(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$
2. $A \cup B = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x) \vee \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \vee \sigma_B(x), \nu_A(x) \wedge \nu_B(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$

Definition 2.5 [6] Let X be a non-empty set and τ_N be the collection of Neutrosophic subsets of X satisfying the following properties:

1. $0_N, 1_N \in \tau_N$
2. $T_1 \cap T_2 \in \tau_N$ for any $T_1, T_2 \in \tau_N$
3. $\cup T_i \in \tau_N$ for every $\{T_i : i \in j\} \subseteq \tau_N$

Then the space (X, τ_N) is called a Neutrosophic Topological Space (NTS). The elements of τ_N are called Neutrosophic Open Set (NOS) and its complement is Neutrosophic Closed Set (NCS).

Definition 2.6 [6] Let (X, τ_N) be a NTS and $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ be a NS in X . Then

Neutrosophic closure of A is $N_Cl(A) = \cap \{ M : M \text{ is a NCS in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq M \}$

Neutrosophic interior of A is $N_Int(A) = \cup \{ H : H \text{ is a NOS in } X \text{ and } H \subseteq A \}$

Definition 2.7 Let (X, τ_N) be a NTS and $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ be a NS in X . Then A is said to be

- Neutrosophic Semi closed set [4] (NSCS) if $N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq A$.
- Neutrosophic Semi open set [4] (NSOS) if $A \subseteq N_Cl(N_Int(A))$.
- Neutrosophic Pre closed set [12] (NPCS) if $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \subseteq A$.
- Neutrosophic Pre open set [12] (NPOS) if $A \subseteq N_Int(N_Cl(A))$.
- Neutrosophic Regular closed set [7] (NRCS) if $A = N_Cl(N_Int(A))$.
- Neutrosophic Regular open set [7] (NROS) if $A = N_Int(N_Cl(A))$.
- Neutrosophic α closed set [5] ($N\alpha$ CS) if $N_Cl(N_Int(N_Cl(A))) \subseteq A$.
- Neutrosophic α open set [5] ($N\alpha$ OS) if $A \subseteq N_Int(N_Cl(N_Int(A)))$.
- Neutrosophic β closed set [8] ($N\beta$ CS) if $N_Int(N_Cl(N_Int(A))) \subseteq A$.
- Neutrosophic β open set [8] ($N\beta$ OS in short) if $A \subseteq N_Cl(N_Int(N_Cl(A)))$.
- Neutrosophic b closed set [6] (Nb CS) if $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq A$

- Neutrosophic b open set [6] (NbOS) if $A \subseteq N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \cup N_Cl(N_Int(A))$
- Neutrosophic π closed set [9] if A is the union of Neutrosophic Regular closed sets.
- Neutrosophic π open set [9] if A is the union of Neutrosophic Regular open sets.

Definition 2.8 Let (X, τ_N) be a NTS and $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ be a NS in X . Then A is said to be

- Neutrosophic Generalized closed set [3] (NGCS) if $N_Cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is a NOS in X .
- Neutrosophic Generalized semi closed set [3] (NGSCS) if $N_sCl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is a NOS in X .
- Neutrosophic α Generalized closed set [5] ($N\alpha$ GCS) if $N_alphaCl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is a NOS in X

Remark 2.9 For any Neutrosophic Set A ,

- $N_Cl(A)^c = (N_Int(A))^c$
- $N_Int(A)^c = (N_Cl(A))^c$
- $N_sCl(A)^c = (N_sInt(A))^c$
- $N_sInt(A)^c = (N_sCl(A))^c$
- $N_sCl(A) = A \cup N_Int(N_Cl(A))$
- $N_sInt(A) = A \cap N_Cl(N_Int(A))$
- $N_alphaCl(A) = A \cup N_Cl(N_Int(N_Cl(A)))$
- $N_alphaInt(A) = A \cap N_Int(N_Cl(N_Int(A)))$

Remark 2.10

1. Each NOS is NPOS in NTS.
2. Each NRCS is NCS in NTS.
3. Each $N\pi$ OS is NOS in NTS.

3. Neutrosophic $\pi\gamma^*$ closed sets in Neutrosophic Topological Spaces

We have introduced Neutrosophic $\pi\gamma^*$ closed sets and explored some of their properties.

Definition 3.1. A Neutrosophic Set A in (X, τ_N) is said to be a Neutrosophic $\pi\gamma^*$ closed sets ($N\pi\gamma^*$ CS in short) if $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $N\pi$ OS in (X, τ_N) .

Example 3.2. Let $X = \{p, q\}$ with $\tau_N = \{0_N, B, 1_N\}$ be a NTS on X , where $B = \langle x, (0.4, 0.5, 0.7), (0.4, 0.4, 0.6) \rangle$. Let us consider the NS, $A = \langle x, (0.3, 0.2, 0.7), (0.3, 0.2, 0.8) \rangle$. Here $N\pi$ OS is $U = \{1_N, B\}$. Clearly $A \subseteq U$. Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) = 0_N \subseteq U$. Therefore NS, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*$ CS in (X, τ_N) .

Theorem 3.3. Every NCS in (X, τ_N) is a $N\pi\gamma^*$ CS (X, τ_N) but not conversely in general.

Proof: Consider ' A ' is a NCS in (X, τ_N) . Assume that $A \subseteq U$ and U is a $N\pi$ OS in (X, τ_N) . Since A is a NCS in (X, τ_N) , $N_Cl(A) = A$. Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) = N_Int(A) \cap N_Int(A) = N_Int(A) \subseteq A \subseteq U$. Thus $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq U$, whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $N\pi$ OS in (X, τ_N) Therefore, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*$ CS in (X, τ_N) . However, the reverse implication is not true.

Example 3.4. Let $X = \{p, q\}$ with $\tau_N = \{0_N, B, 1_N\}$ be a NTS on X , where $B = \langle x, (0.2, 0.4, 0.6), (0.3, 0.5, 0.7) \rangle$. Let us consider the NS, $A = \langle x, (0.1, 0.3, 0.8), (0.2, 0.4, 0.7) \rangle$. Here $N\pi OS$ is $U = \{1_N, B\}$. Clearly $A \subseteq U$. Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) = 0_N \subseteq U$. But $N_Cl(A) = B^c \not\subseteq A$. Therefore NS, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ but not NCS in (X, τ_N) .

Theorem 3.5. Every NSCS in (X, τ_N) is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ (X, τ_N) but not conversely in general.

Proof: Consider A is a NSCS in (X, τ_N) . Suppose that $A \subseteq U$ and U is a $N\pi OS$ in (X, τ_N) . Since A is a NSCS in (X, τ_N) , $N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq A$. Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap A \subseteq N_Cl(A) \cap A = A \subseteq U$. Thus $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq U$, whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $N\pi OS$ in (X, τ_N) . Therefore, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) . However, the reverse implication is not true.

Example 3.6. Let $X = \{p, q\}$ with $\tau_N = \{0_N, B, 1_N\}$ be a NTS on X , where $B = \langle x, (0.2, 0.4, 0.6), (0.3, 0.5, 0.7) \rangle$. Let us consider the NS, $A = \langle x, (0.1, 0.3, 0.8), (0.2, 0.4, 0.7) \rangle$. Here $N\pi OS$ is $U = \{1_N, B\}$. Clearly $A \subseteq U$. Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) = 0_N \subseteq U$. But $N_Int(N_Cl(A)) = B \not\subseteq A$. Therefore NS, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ but not NSCS in (X, τ_N) .

Theorem 3.7. Every NPCS in (X, τ_N) is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ (X, τ_N) but not conversely in general.

Proof: Consider A is a NPCS in (X, τ_N) . Suppose that $A \subseteq U$ and U is a $N\pi OS$ in (X, τ_N) . Since A is a NPCS in (X, τ_N) , $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \subseteq A$. Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq A \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq A \cap N_Cl(A) = A \subseteq U$. Thus $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq U$, whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $N\pi OS$ in (X, τ_N) . Therefore, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) . However, the reverse implication is not true.

Example 3.8. Let $X = \{p, q\}$ with $\tau_N = \{0_N, B_1, B_2, 1_N\}$ be a NTS on X , where $B_1 = \langle x, (0.5, 0.5, 0.5), (0.6, 0.5, 0.4) \rangle$ and $B_2 = \langle x, (0.4, 0.5, 0.6), (0.3, 0.5, 0.7) \rangle$. Let us consider the NS, $A = \langle x, (0.4, 0.5, 0.6), (0.4, 0.5, 0.6) \rangle$. Here $N\pi OS$ is $U = \{1_N, B_1, B_2\}$. Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) = B_2 \subseteq U$. But $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) = B_1^c \not\subseteq A$. Therefore NS, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ but not NPCS in (X, τ_N) .

Theorem 3.9. Every NRCS in (X, τ_N) is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) but not conversely in general.

Proof: Let A be a NRCS in (X, τ_N) . Since every NRCS is a NCS, by Theorem 3.3 A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) . However, the reverse implication is not true.

Example 3.10. Let $X = \{p, q\}$ with $\tau_N = \{0_N, B, 1_N\}$ be a NTS on X , where $B = \langle x, (0.5, 0.5, 0.5), (0.4, 0.5, 0.6) \rangle$. Let us consider the NS, $A = \langle x, (0.5, 0.5, 0.5), (0.5, 0.5, 0.4) \rangle$. Here $N\pi OS$ is $U = \{1_N, B\}$. Clearly $A \subseteq U$. Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) = B \subseteq U$. But $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) = B^c \neq A$. Therefore NS, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ but not NRCS in (X, τ_N) .

Theorem 3.11. Every NROS in (X, τ_N) is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) but not conversely in general.

Proof: Let A be a NROS in (X, τ_N) . A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) . Then $N_Int(N_Cl(A)) = A$ and $N_Int(A) = A$. Suppose that $A \subseteq U$ and U is a $N\pi OS$ in (X, τ_N) . Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq N_Cl(A) \cap A = A \subseteq U$. Thus $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq U$, whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $N\pi OS$ in (X, τ_N) . Therefore, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) . However, the reverse implication is not true.

Example 3.12. Let $X = \{p, q\}$ with $\tau_N = \{0_N, B, 1_N\}$ be a NTS on X , where $B = \langle x, (0.5, 0.5, 0.5), (0.4, 0.5, 0.6) \rangle$. Let us consider the NS, $A = \langle x, (0.4, 0.5, 0.6), (0.4, 0.5, 0.6) \rangle$. Here

$N\pi OS$ is $U = \{1_N, B\}$. Clearly $A \subseteq U$. Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) = 0_N \subseteq U$. But $N_Int(N_Cl(A)) = B \neq A$. Therefore NS, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ but not $NR OS$ in (X, τ_N) .

Theorem 3.13. Every $N\alpha CS$ in (X, τ_N) is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ (X, τ_N) but not conversely in general.

Proof: Consider A is a $N\alpha CS$ in (X, τ_N) . Suppose that $A \subseteq U$ and U is a $N\pi OS$ in (X, τ_N) . Since A is a $N\alpha CS$ in (X, τ_N) , $N_Cl(N_Int(N_Cl(A))) \subseteq A$. Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq N_Cl(N_Int(N_Cl(A))) \cap N_Cl(N_Int(N_Cl(A))) \subseteq A \cap A = A \subseteq U$. Thus $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq U$, whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $N\pi OS$ in (X, τ_N) . Therefore, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) . However, the reverse implication is not true.

Example 3.14. Let $X = \{ p, q \}$ with $\tau_N = \{ 0_N, B, 1_N \}$ be a NTS on X , where $B = \langle x, (0.5,0.5,0.5), (0.4,0.5,0.6) \rangle$. Let us consider the NS, $A = \langle x, (0.4,0.5,0.4), (0.5,0.5,0.6) \rangle$. Here $N\pi OS$ is $U = \{1_N, B\}$. Clearly $A \subseteq U$. Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) = 0_N \subseteq U$. But $N_Cl(N_Int(N_Cl(A))) = B^c \not\subseteq A$. Therefore NS, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ but not $N\alpha CS$ in (X, τ_N) .

Theorem 3.15. Every $NbCS$ in (X, τ_N) is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ (X, τ_N) , but not conversely in general.

Proof: Consider A is a $NbCS$ in (X, τ_N) . Suppose that $A \subseteq U$ and U is a $N\pi OS$ in (X, τ_N) . Since A is a $NbCS$ in (X, τ_N) , $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq A$. Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq A \subseteq U$. Thus $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq U$, whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $N\pi OS$ in (X, τ_N) . Therefore, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) . However, the reverse implication is not true.

Example 3.16. Let $X = \{ p, q \}$ with $\tau_N = \{ 0_N, B_1, B_2, 1_N \}$ be a NTS on X , where $B_1 = \langle x, (0.5,0.5,0.5), (0.6,0.5,0.4) \rangle$ and $B_2 = \langle x, (0.4,0.5,0.6), (0.3,0.5,0.7) \rangle$. Let us consider the NS, $A = \langle x, (0.4,0.5,0.6), (0.6,0.5,0.4) \rangle$. Here $N\pi OS$ is $U = \{1_N, B_1, B_2\}$. Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$. But $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) = B_1^c \not\subseteq A$. Therefore NS, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ but not $NbCS$ in (X, τ_N) .

Theorem 3.17. Every $NGCS$ in (X, τ_N) is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) but not conversely.

Proof: Consider A is a $NGCS$ in (X, τ_N) . Assume that $A \subseteq U$ and U is a $N\pi OS$ in (X, τ_N) . Since A is a $NGCS$ in (X, τ_N) , $N_Cl(A) \subseteq U$. Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq N_Cl(A) \subseteq U$. Thus $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq U$, whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $N\pi OS$ in (X, τ_N) . Therefore, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) . However, the reverse implication is not true.

Example 3.18. Let $X = \{ p, q \}$ with $\tau_N = \{ 0_N, B, 1_N \}$ be a NTS on X , where $B = \langle x, (0.3,0.5,0.4), (0.2,0.5,0.3) \rangle$. Consider NS, $A = \langle x, (0.2,0.4,0.6), (0.2,0.4,0.4) \rangle$. Here $N\pi OS$ $U = \{1_N, B\}$. Clearly $A \subseteq U$. Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) = 0_N \subseteq U$. But $N_Cl(A) = B^c \not\subseteq B$, whenever $A \subseteq B$. Therefore NS, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ but not $NGCS$ in (X, τ_N) .

Theorem 3.19. Every $NGSCS$ in (X, τ_N) is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) but not conversely.

Proof: Consider ' A ' is a $NGSCS$ in (X, τ_N) . Assume that $A \subseteq U$ and U is a $N\pi OS$ in (X, τ_N) . Since A is a $NGSCS$ in (X, τ_N) , $N_sCl(A) = A \cup N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq U$. This implies $N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq U$. Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap U \subseteq U$. Thus $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq U$, whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $N\pi OS$ in (X, τ_N) . Therefore, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) . However, the reverse implication is not true.

Example 3.20. Let $X = \{ p, q \}$ with $\tau_N = \{ 0_N, B_1, B_2, 1_N \}$ be a NTS on X , where $B_1 = \langle x, (0.5,0.5,0.5), (0.3,0.5,0.7) \rangle$ and $B_2 = \langle x, (0.4,0.5,0.6), (0.3,0.5,0.7) \rangle$. Let us consider the NS, $A = \langle x, (0.3,0.5,0.4), (0.2,0.5,0.8) \rangle$. Here $N\pi OS$ is $U = \{1_N, B_1, B_2\}$. Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq U$.

$(N_Cl(A)) = 0_N \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$. But $N_sCl(A) = A \cup N_Int(N_Cl(A)) = A \cup B_1 = B_1 \not\subseteq B$ and $A \subseteq B_2$. Therefore NS, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ but not NGSCS in (X, τ_N) .

Theorem 3.21. Every $N\alpha GCS$ in (X, τ_N) is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ (X, τ_N) but not conversely in general.

Proof: Consider A is a $N\alpha GCS$ in (X, τ_N) . Suppose that $A \subseteq U$ and U is a $N\pi OS$ in (X, τ_N) . Since A is a $N\alpha GCS$ in (X, τ_N) , $N_Cl(A) \subseteq U$. Therefore $A \cup N_Cl(N_Int(N_Cl(A))) \subseteq U$, so $N_Cl(N_Int(N_Cl(A))) \subseteq U$ and $N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq U$. Now $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap U \subseteq U$. Thus $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq U$, whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $N\pi OS$ in (X, τ_N) . Therefore, A is a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) . However, the reverse implication is not true.

Example 3.22. In Example 3.20, the NS $A = \langle x, (0.3,0.5,0.7), (0.2,0.5,0.8) \rangle$ is $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) but not a $N\alpha GCS$ in (X, τ_N) as $N_Cl(A) = A \cup N_Cl(N_Int(N_Cl(A))) = A \cup B_1^c = B_1^c \not\subseteq B_1, B_2$ and $A \subseteq B_1, B_2$.

In the following figure (a) we have provided relation between $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ and other closed sets in Neutrosophic topological space.

Figure (a)

Remark 3.23. The union of two $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ s need not be a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) in general.

Example 3.24. Let $X = \{p, q\}$ with $\tau_N = \{0_N, B_1, B_2, 1_N\}$ be a NTS on X, where $B_1 = \langle x, (0.4,0.5,0.6), (0.2,0.5,0.8) \rangle$ and $B_2 = \langle x, (0.4,0.5,0.5), (0.4,0.5,0.5) \rangle$. Here $A = \langle x, (0.4,0.5,0.5), (0.5,0.5,0.4) \rangle$ and $B = \langle x, (0.5,0.5,0.4), (0.2,0.5,0.6) \rangle$ are $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) , but $A \cup B = \langle x, (0.5,0.5,0.4), (0.5,0.5,0.4) \rangle$ is not a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) .

Theorem 3.25. Let (X, τ_N) be a NTS. Then for every $A \in N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) and for every $B \in NS$ in (X, τ_N) , $A \subseteq B \subseteq N_Cl(N_Int(A))$ which implies $B \in N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) .

Proof: Let $B \subseteq U$ and U be an $N\pi OS$ in X. Since $A \subseteq B$, $A \subseteq U$. Also, $B \subseteq N_Cl(N_Int(A))$ which implies $N_Cl(N_Int(B)) \subseteq N_Cl(N_Int(A))$. Now $N_Int(N_Cl(B)) \subseteq N_Int(N_Cl(A))$. Therefore $N_Cl(N_Int(B)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(B)) \subseteq N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq U$, by hypothesis. Hence $B \in N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) .

Theorem 3.26. If A is both $N\pi OS$ and $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) then A is a NbCS in (X, τ_N) .

Proof: Let A be a $N\pi OS$ and a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) . Then $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq A$, as $A \subseteq A$, by hypothesis. Therefore $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq A$. Hence A is a $N\beta CS$ in (X, τ_N) .

Theorem 3.27. If A is both a $N\pi OS$ and a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) then A is a $N\beta CS$ in (X, τ_N) .

Proof: Let A be a $N\pi OS$ and a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) . Then $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq A$, as $A \subseteq A$, by hypothesis. Now $N_Int(N_Cl(N_Int(A))) = N_Int(N_Cl(N_Int(A))) \cap N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \subseteq N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \cap N_Cl(N_Int(A)) = N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq A$. Therefore $N_Int(N_Cl(N_Int(A))) \subseteq A$. Hence A is a $N\beta CS$ in (X, τ_N) .

Theorem 3.28. If A is both a $N\pi OS$ and a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) then A is a $NSCS$ in (X, τ_N) .

Proof: Let A be a $N\pi OS$ and a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) . That is A is a NOS in (X, τ_N) . Then $N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq A$, as $A \subseteq A$, by hypothesis. Clearly $N_Int(N_Cl(A)) = N_Cl(A) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) = N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \cap N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq A$. Therefore $N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \subseteq A$. Hence A is a $NSCS$ in (X, τ_N) .

Theorem 3.29. If A is both a $N\pi OS$ and a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) , then A is a $NROS$ in (X, τ_N) .

Proof: Let A be a $N\pi OS$ and a $N\pi\gamma^*CS$ in (X, τ_N) . That is A is a NOS in (X, τ_N) . Then $N_Int(N_Cl(A)) = N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \cap N_Cl(A) = N_Int(N_Cl(A)) \cap N_Cl(N_Int(A)) \subseteq A$. Since A is a NOS , it is a $NPOS$ and $A \subseteq N_Int(N_Cl(A))$. Therefore $A = N_Int(N_Cl(A))$. Hence A is a $NRCS$ in (X, τ_N) .

4. Conclusion: In this paper we have introduced Neutrosophic $\pi\gamma^*$ closed sets in Neutrosophic Topological Spaces and discussed some of its properties and some contradicting examples. This idea can be developed and extended in the area of continuous functions, homeomorphisms, compactness and connected and so on.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Acknowledgements: The authors are highly grateful to the Referees for their consecutive suggestions.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Atanassov, K. Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, 1986,20, 87–94.
- [2] Florentin Smarandache, Neutrosophic Set, A Generalization of the Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set. *Journal of Defense Resources Management*, 2010, 1(1), 107–116.
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354204356>
- [3] Iswarya, P; Bageerathi, K. A Study on Neutrosophic Generalized Semi-Closed Sets in Neutrosophic Topological Spaces. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 2019, 6(2), 452–457. www.jetir.org
- [4] Iswarya, P; Bageerathi, K. On Neutrosophic Semi-Open sets in Neutrosophic Topological Spaces. *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology*, 2019, 37(3), 24–33.
<http://www.ijmtjournal.org>

- [5] Jayanthi, D. α Generalized Closed Sets in Neutrosophic Topological Spaces. *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology (IJMTT)*, 2018, *Special Issue*, 88–92. <http://www.ijmtjournal.org>
- [6] Maheswari, C; Sathyabama, M; Chandrasekar, S. Neutrosophic generalized b-closed sets in Neutrosophic topological spaces. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2018, 1139(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1139/1/012065>
- [7] Mohammed Ali Jaffer, I ; Ramesh, K. Neutrosophic Generalized Pre Regular Closed Sets. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 2019, 30, 171–181. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3569681>
- [8] Narmatha, S; Glory Bebina, E; Vishnu Priya, R. On $\pi g\beta$ -Closed Sets and Mappings in Neutrosophic Topological Spaces. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, 2019, 8(12S), 505–510. <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijitee.l1126.10812s19>
- [9] Poornima, R; Girija, S; Gayathri, C; Gayathri, P. *A study of Neutrosophic Rg- closed sets*, IIP Series. e-ISBN: 978-93-6252-737-0, Book 2, Part 3, Chapter 1, 2024,3,67-94
- [10] Sakthivel, K; Manikandan, M. $\pi g\gamma^*$ closed Sets in Intuitionistic Fuzzy Topological Spaces. *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology*, 2019, 65(3), 167–174. <http://www.ijmtjournal.org>
- [11] Salama, A. A; Albowi, S. A. Neutrosophic Set and Neutrosophic Topological Spaces. *IOSR Journal of Mathematics*, 2012, 3(4), 31–35. <https://doi.org/10.9790/5728-0343135>
- [12] Venkateswara Rao, V; Srinivasa Rao, Y. Neutrosophic Pre-open Sets and Pre-closed Sets in Neutrosophic Topology. *International Journal of Chem Tech Research*, 2017, 10(10), 449–458.
- [13] Zadeh, L. A. Fuzzy Sets*. *Information and Control*, 1965, 8, 338–353.

Received: July 16, 2025. Accepted: Dec 15, 2025